

Antenna Range Upgrade Project - Indoor Doppler Antenna Test Range

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Abstract - The Indoor Doppler Antenna Test Range at Robins Air Force Base, Georgia, was constructed in the mid-1970's to provide an automated test and calibration capability for the APN-185 and APN-189 navigational Doppler radar antennas. Over time, the capabilities of the facility were gradually enhanced to enable test/calibration of a variety of antennas used in navigation, terrain following, and fire control systems. In the late 1980's, a project was undertaken to upgrade the facility by replacing obsolete hardware components and by redesigning the system software and rehosting it in Ada. The project, which was completed in the spring of 1993, has resulted in notable improvements in system reliability, maintainability, and performance.

I. INTRODUCTION.

In the early 1970's, the Air Force employed two types of Doppler navigational radar systems in its F-111 aircraft. The APN-185 system was used by the Strategic Air Command on the FB-111, and the APN-189 system was used by the Tactical Air Command on the F-111D. Both systems employed eight-element beam pattern antenna arrays which required electrical calibration. At that time, a flight test procedure was the only available means of electrically calibrating these antennas. This procedure involved flying the antenna to be calibrated over an accurately-surveyed ground track while collecting appropriate electronic and photographic data. Laboratory analysis of the data was then performed to arrive at the desired calibration components [1]. The flight test calibration procedure produced an acceptable level of measurement accuracy, but was costly, time-consuming, and was subject to the adverse effects of poor weather conditions.

The problems associated with flight testing prompted the Air Force to hire General Dynamics Corporation to search for an alternative means of Doppler antenna calibration. General Dynamics studied various outdoor test range configurations, surveyed commercially available technologies, and considered the feasibility of an indoor test

range. Studies of far field outdoor range configurations indicated that such a range would be feasible, but would also have at least two major limitations - 1) it would produce angular accuracies which were only marginally acceptable and, 2) it would fail to solve problems resulting from adverse weather conditions. Studies of commercially available products - including compact antenna ranges, RF anechoic chambers, precision positioner systems, and seismic isolation platforms - suggested that it was feasible to construct an indoor Doppler test range which would be free of the limitations of a comparable outdoor range.

In March of 1974, General Dynamics submitted a proposal for construction of an indoor Doppler antenna test range at Robins AFB, Georgia. Construction of the facility began in the summer of 1974 and was completed in March of 1976. Initial tests indicated that the indoor range exhibited characteristics equivalent to those of an outdoor range 1494 meters (4900 feet) in length. Additional performance testing indicated that the system was capable of achieving calibration accuracies of approximately 6 arc-seconds, a three-to-one improvement over the results obtained on the flight test range [1].

II. FACILITY DESCRIPTION.

The Indoor Doppler Antenna Test Range is a three-room complex consisting of an anechoic chamber, a control room, and a utility room. The major functional components of the test facility include an RF absorption system, compact antenna range, antenna positioner system, seismic isolation system, computer system, RF system, and environmental control system.

The RF absorption system serves to reduce RF measurement errors by preventing stray RF energy from reaching the antenna under test (AUT). The system consists of numerous RF absorptive panels which are mounted on the walls and ceiling of the anechoic chamber and also on the mast of the antenna positioner assembly. The anechoic chamber and RF

absorptive panels are designed to provide a cylindrical RF quiet zone four feet in diameter and six feet in length which is centered about the point at which the AUT attaches to the antenna positioner assembly.

The compact antenna range creates a simulated far field RF environment for AUT testing. The compact range is located in the anechoic chamber and consists of a parabolic reflector and an RF feed system, both of which are mounted on a seismically stable platform. Far field conditions are simulated by using the reflector to convert the spherical wavefront generated by the RF feed system to a plane wave which is then used to provide the stimulus for the AUT.

Precision control of AUT orientation is provided by the antenna positioner system. This system consists of two major subsystems - the antenna positioner assembly and the antenna positioner console assembly. The positioner assembly, which is located in the anechoic chamber, is a four-axis servo-controlled pedestal which is mounted on a seismically stable platform. The function of the positioner assembly is to provide highly accurate positioning of the AUT during testing. The console assembly, which is located in the control room, consists of several bays of electronics which control the motion of the positioner assembly.

The seismic isolation system minimizes the effects of building vibration on the calibration process. The principal components of the system are a concrete stable platform, a set of pneumatic isolators, and an air compressor. The stable platform, which is recessed into the floor of the anechoic chamber, is a 48-ton concrete slab upon which both the compact antenna range and the positioner assembly are mounted. The isolators, which are located under the stable platform, prevent the platform from making direct contact with the chamber floor. Seismic isolation is achieved by filling the isolators with compressed air, thereby suspending the stable platform, and the equipment mounted on it, a short distance above the floor of the anechoic chamber.

The computer system, which is located in the control room, governs the operation of all remotely controlled instruments in the test facility via an IEEE-488 bus. These instruments include the antenna positioner system, network analyzer, and RF switches. In addition to performing instrument control functions, the computer system performs data analysis, stores information, and provides the operator interface to the calibration system.

The RF system produces microwave stimulus signals of the appropriate frequencies, amplifies them when necessary, and conveys them either to the RF feed system in the anechoic

chamber (for transmission measurements) or directly to the AUT (for reflection measurements). The system also receives response signals from the AUT and analyzes them to determine the transmission or reflection characteristics of the AUT. The RF system is located in the control room and has the network analyzer, RF source, traveling wave tube amplifier, and test set as its principal components.

The environmental control system, which is located in the utility room, monitors and controls the temperature and humidity within the anechoic chamber and control room. Control of environmental conditions is necessary to provide optimal conditions for instrument operation and antenna calibration.

The test facility is used primarily for antenna boresight and pattern testing. The steps involved in a typical antenna calibration procedure are:

1. The operator invokes the antenna test executive on the system computer and performs any required RF and positioner calibration procedures.
2. The operator then selects the desired test procedure and mounts the AUT on the antenna positioner assembly using the appropriate mounting adapter.
3. The test system, operating under the control of the system computer, causes RF energy of the appropriate frequency to be radiated into the anechoic chamber, orients the antenna as appropriate, and makes antenna gain measurements.
4. When the measurements are complete, the RF energy is turned off, the antenna measurement data is analyzed, and the results are displayed on the computer monitor.
5. The operator examines the test results and adjusts/retests the AUT as required to achieve proper calibration.
6. At the conclusion of the test, the operator generates a printed copy of the final test results and removes the AUT from the antenna positioner assembly.

III. RATIONALE FOR THE UPGRADE.

A. *System Performance Issues*

By the late 1980's, the capabilities of the indoor Doppler range had been enhanced to enable test/calibration of a diverse assemblage of antennas, including Doppler velocity sensors, terrain following antennas, and fire control

antennas. Since calibration is a critical step in the depot maintenance of these antennas, it is essential that the antenna test system be highly reliable and maintainable. Unfortunately, the reliability of several critical system components, most notably the network analyzer and system computer, had deteriorated significantly over the years resulting in frequent system failures and excessive amounts of system downtime. Also, the system computer's slow speed and limited memory capacity (32K RAM) imposed severe limitations on test system performance.

Not only was system performance being adversely affected by hardware-related problems, but by software-related problems as well. The limitations of the test system programming language, ATS BASIC, made test program sets (TPSs) difficult to read and interpret, thereby making software maintenance and modification a tedious and time-consuming process. This problem was further complicated by a general lack of external TPS documentation. The rigidity of the software design also presented problems by limiting the operator's test options, particularly in the area of error recovery. In general, a fatal error encountered during testing required the operator to repeat the entire test procedure, including those portions not affected by the error.

To remedy the aforementioned reliability and maintainability problems, a major system hardware/software upgrade was proposed in early 1988. At that time, it was determined that a feasibility study should be conducted to determine the scope of the proposed upgrade, to propose a plan of action, to identify required skills and tools, and to estimate cost and schedule.

B. Feasibility Study

The antenna range upgrade feasibility study was conducted during the summer and fall of 1988. Analysis of the performance and supportability of the test system hardware indicated that three of the major subsystems - the RF system, computer system, and antenna positioner system - should be considered for modification or replacement. The RF and computer systems were found to have serious deficiencies in the areas of reliability and supportability and it was readily apparent that these systems should be completely replaced. Deficiencies in the antenna positioner system were not sufficiently serious to warrant system replacement, and it was therefore decided to address these deficiencies through system modification. Analysis of the test system software (TPSs and instrument drivers) indicated that significant improvements in software reliability and maintainability could only be achieved by first redesigning the software using modern software engineering practices and then recoding it using a modern high-order language.

Once the scope of the upgrade had been defined, a list of overall system requirements was assembled. Several replacement options for the existing Hewlett-Packard (HP) 8542B network analyzer system were considered and were evaluated based upon their ability to meet the stated requirements. In like manner, several replacement options for the existing HP 2100S computer system were also considered. Since Air Force policy required that Ada be used for all major software upgrades, Ada was the only software language given serious consideration.

The final phase of the study involved demonstrating the capability to design and produce Ada code which would perform the key functions of the existing TPSs and instrument drivers. Prototypic Ada code was successfully developed which was capable of producing data plots, performing standard data analysis, storing and retrieving data, and controlling instruments via an IEEE-488 bus.

The key recommendations resulting from the study were:

- that the antenna test system be restructured to support instrument control via a standard IEEE-488 bus.
- that the existing HP 8542B network analyzer and its associated components be replaced with an HP 8510 B network analyzer, HP 8340B synthesized sweeper, HP 8511A frequency converter, HP 11691D dual directional coupler, and several HP 59306A relay actuators.
- that the existing HP 2100S computer and its associated components be replaced with a Digital Equipment Corporation (DEC) VAXstation 3500 computer, LG31 line printer, and TU81 magnetic tape subsystem.
- that the existing Carco P-390G antenna positioner system be modified to include an IEEE-488 bus interface.
- that the existing ATS BASIC programs and assembly language instrument drivers be redesigned and rehosted in Ada.

IV. PERFORMANCE OF THE UPGRADE.

The system upgrade began in the spring of 1989 with identification of top-level software requirements and development of a top-level software design. Software development activities continued through the spring of 1992 when the last of seven TPSs was completed. Final system

integration and testing began in the early summer of 1992 and concluded in December of 1992 when the obsolete system components were removed and the system was placed in its final operating configuration. Final acceptance testing took place in the spring of 1993.

A. Hardware-Related Activities

In the summer of 1990, the new RF and computer components arrived at Robins AFB. Initially, the equipment was placed in a software laboratory where it was used for development of I/O routines and instrument drivers. After a time, the equipment was moved to the antenna range where it was integrated with the existing equipment. A dual operating configuration was established which permitted the system to be operated in its original mode for production activities and in its upgraded mode for integration and testing of the Ada TPSs and instrument drivers. The dual configuration permitted the system to be switched from one operating mode to the other in less than five minutes.

The hardware integration process was performed in close cooperation with antenna range personnel to avoid unnecessary interference with normal antenna production activities. The only significant impact on production occurred when the positioner system's reference chassis was removed and shipped to the manufacturer for modification.

B. Software-Related Activities

The software portion of the upgrade began with a thorough software requirements analysis which addressed requirements for the overall system, TPSs, and instrument drivers. Basic TPS and instrument driver requirements were identified through reverse engineering of the existing ATS BASIC and assembly language code. Deficiencies in the TPSs and drivers were identified through consultation with antenna range personnel and new software requirements were added to address these deficiencies. Throughout the requirements analysis phase emphasis was placed on developing requirements which would promote flexibility, efficiency, productivity, and waste reduction.

A top-down structured design approach was used to develop a framework for the new software. The overall design objectives were to create a pool of reusable resources - including instrument drivers, data analysis routines, and commonly used I/O routines - to support test program development and to create a set of instrument-independent test programs. To this end, two computer software configuration items (CSCIs), the Test Program CSCI and System CSCI, were established and were then decomposed into various computer software components (CSCs) and computer software units (CSUs). Requirements were then

assigned to the appropriate CSCs and CSUs. As the design process progressed, antenna range personnel were consulted frequently to further refine requirements and to ensure that the design, and in particular the I/O format, would meet the user's requirements.

The CSU coding phase began with the development of coding standards and guidelines. These standards and guidelines addressed a variety of topics, including general format, use of comments, naming conventions, and software engineering practices. Emphasis was placed on developing modular, well-structured, and well-documented code which would be both reliable and maintainable. Initial coding and testing was performed off-line on a Rational R1000 or mainframe VAX. As software units became further refined, they were transferred to the VAXstation for recompilation, integration, and testing.

V. RESULTS.

Full-time use of the upgraded system for antenna production began in early December of 1992 and sufficient time has now elapsed to enable an accurate assessment of the impact of the system upgrade. The following are some of the more significant results:

- Diminished system downtime

System downtime resulting from RF and computer system malfunctions has been virtually eliminated. Downtime attributable to malfunctions in the antenna positioner system has also been reduced as a result of the improved bus interface.

- Reduced waste of material

In many cases, the original test system required the use of a printer or plotter for reporting of test results. It was not uncommon for routine calibration procedures to produce copious amounts of hard-copy output, most of which was later discarded. The expense of the printer/plotter paper coupled with its non-recyclable nature made this practice particularly wasteful.

The Ada software was designed to permit the operator to perform all test and calibration procedures using the CRT alone. Production of hard-copy output is permitted, but not required. Waste reduction has been achieved by producing only essential hard-copy output and by using inexpensive, recyclable printer paper.

- Enhanced productivity

Several features of the system hardware and software have resulted in enhanced system productivity. The high processing speed of the VAXstation and the automation of various test procedures which were previously performed manually have significantly reduced the time required for antenna calibration. In addition, various software design features - such as continuous audible alarms and completion time estimation - have contributed to minimizing the amount of wasted production time.

- Enhanced error isolation and reporting

Significant improvements in software/hardware error isolation and reporting have resulted from the inclusion of exception handlers in the TPSs and instrument drivers. The handlers report the nature of the problem and the hardware/software component(s) responsible. Many also provide suggestions for corrective action.

Error reporting has been further enhanced through the addition of an antenna test log file which records test information and error messages produced during TPS execution. The log file aids in error resolution by providing software support personnel with a reliable description of the error and of the events preceding it.

- Improved TPS flexibility and ease of system operation

The test station, in its original configuration, operated in the test-oriented disc system-II (TODS-II) environment. The keyboard was the principal operator interface to the system and the operator was required to have a working knowledge of TODS-II syntax. The new operator interface is window-based, uses a keyboard and mouse, and provides a much more automated approach to system operation. Upon login, the operator invokes a menu system which provides easy access to a variety of system functions - such as setting the system clock, examining an antenna test log file, starting the antenna test executive, or shutting down the computer system. This approach enables a user to successfully operate the test station without having extensive knowledge of the operating system. The improved operator interface and redesigned test procedures manuals have significantly reduced the amount of time required to train new operators.

In general, the original ATS BASIC TPSs were rigidly designed and had few entry points. Some test procedures required hours to run and had no mechanisms for incremental data storage. As a consequence, power failures and system malfunctions sometimes resulted in the loss of significant amounts of test data. The operator's only recourse in such situations was to repeat the entire test

procedure. The limited number of entry points had the additional disadvantage of wasting production time by making it impractical for an operator to initiate lengthy test procedures late in his shift. The Ada software has given the operator much more control over the antenna calibration process. If testing is interrupted for any reason, it can be resumed at a convenient point without extensive loss of data. In most cases, testing can be conducted until the end of the shift, interrupted by the operator, and then resumed at a later time with minimal duplication of effort.

- Simplified software development and maintenance

The readability, modularity, and structured nature of the Ada code have greatly simplified the software modification and maintenance process. The process has been further simplified through the use of reusable software units. During initial development, many of the most commonly used software components were developed as generic units resulting in a pool of reusable code. These generic units have proven to be highly reliable and have been very useful in the software development and modification process.

The original HP 2100S computer was a standalone system and required that all software development and modification be performed at the test station. Antenna production and software development could not, therefore, be performed in parallel. The networking capability of the VAXstation has eliminated this limitation by permitting software to be developed off-line and later transferred to the VAXstation for integration and test.

- Improved monitoring of system performance

Test statistics software has been developed which tracks the types of test procedures performed, the number of times each is performed, and the total amount of time expended on each procedure. Upon completion of AUT testing, the software prompts the operator for comments, summarizes the collected data, and records the information for future reference. This information has proven useful in monitoring calibration system performance and provides a concise record of the steps taken in calibrating each individual AUT. No comparable capability was available in the original test system.

VI. CONCLUSIONS.

This project has demonstrated that Ada can be successfully used as an automatic test language. The attributes of the Ada language enabled the development of TPSs and instrument drivers which are understandable, reliable,

efficient, and modifiable. The ability to create generic programming units in Ada enabled the development of a large pool of reusable software components which should greatly facilitate future development efforts.

Upgrading the antenna test system resulted in significant improvements in performance and supportability. These improvements can be attributed to:

- the greater reliability and supportability of the new hardware components.
- the increased speed and processing capacity of the new hardware components.
- the understandability, reliability, and modifiability of the Ada software.
- the introduction of new instrumentation and software procedures to further automate the calibration process.
- the user-oriented approach to software design and development. This approach permitted many deficiencies to be identified and eliminated and many new and useful features to be added. The system software was redesigned with the goals of correcting known deficiencies, incorporating new features, and taking advantage of the power of the Ada language. These goals would not have been reached had the software been simply "translated" from ATS BASIC to Ada.

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REFERENCES

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